

EFFECTS OF ALCOHOLISM ON FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS**Valide Valiyeva***PhD in psychology, faculty member;
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Alcohol use disorder (AUD) is a common addiction, affecting nearly 15 million adults in the United States (American Addiction center). While alcohol dependence can be devastating to one's health, it can also impact a person's relationships, including the most meaningful people in their life. Alcohol use disorder can lead to lost friendships, estranged marriages and family conflict.

Alcohol addiction has many negative effects on the user's health. According to the "Global Status Report on Alcohol and Health" published by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2011, approximately 2.5 million people lose their lives each year due to alcohol abuse, and in the 2014 report, this number reached 3.3 million.

The main target of the study is search literature materials to learn about the connection between alcohol addiction and relationships and how to prevent or manage relationship issues caused by a drinking problem.

Keywords: alcoholism, family relationship, alcohol addiction, violence in the family

Introduction: Alcoholism disrupts family relationships and harmony. Since alcoholism affects all family members, it has also been defined as a "family disease". In these families, alcohol becomes an inseparable part of the family's daily life. It affects the family's development. It disrupts the family's ability to adapt to changes and crises. The flow of life goes according to the desires of the alcohol-addicted individual. The feelings, desires and needs of other family members are pushed to the background. Individuals' developments may be sacrificed to sustain the family. Violence against spouses is common. Children of alcohol addicts experience feelings of shame and guilt (thinking that they are at fault) in an environment of tension, violence, chaos and turmoil. Children may leave home early. Studies have shown that men growing up in families with alcoholism have alcohol problems, while women experience depression and marital problems.

Alcohol addiction not only harms the user physiologically, but also causes deterioration in family, busi-

ness and social life, and economic situation. Traffic-related crimes, various accidents, and problems such as murder are common (WHO,2014). According to statistics from the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration of the United States (US), it is stated that in 2016, 10,497 people lost their lives in fatal accidents caused by drunk drivers, and this corresponds to 28% of all traffic accident deaths (National Center for Statistics and Analysis, 2016). In a study evaluating victims of violence who applied to an emergency room in Norway, it was determined that 53% of the perpetrators had consumed alcohol before the attack.

The impact of alcohol on relationships is widespread and can affect every single relationship a person is a part of. From intimacy problems and lack of emotional availability to the financial burden and negative effects on children, alcohol use disorder can affect partners, their children and other family members. The effects of alcohol addiction on family relationship are described in following picture:

Picture 1. Effects of alcohol addiction on family environment

It is a disorder characterized by drinking alcohol excessively and repeatedly, disrupting physical and mental health, family, social and work harmony, and the inability to control the desire to drink alcohol and to stop drinking alcohol. However, it cannot be said that everyone who drinks alcohol is sick. It is not always easy to distinguish between a social drinker or “evening person” and alcoholism. Various physical diseases are seen in people who are addicted to alcohol. Liver damage, severe deterioration in the stomach-intestine and pancreas, high blood pressure, heart muscle disorders, brain and cerebellum damage are some of them. Alcohol withdrawal crises, dementia, hallucinations, extreme skepticism, irritability, insomnia and sexual dysfunctions can be seen by negatively affecting mental health. Various factors play a role in the development of alcoholism. Those who experience extreme anxiety or pessimism sometimes use alcohol as a sedative and relaxing “medicine”. However, this attitude leads to the development of alcohol addiction. Especially in young people, the craving for alcoholic drinks, the influence of the social environment and the influence of peers and friends are also important. Alcohol addiction is a disorder that is most often seen in men between the ages of 22-35.

Unhealthy family dynamics that develop in families with alcohol problems may have their own unique aspects:

- Sometimes the attitudes and behaviors of other family members unintentionally encourage alcohol consumption.
- Sometimes, unhealthy defense mechanisms are established to continue family life.
- In families with alcohol problems, “silent rules” also develop. Rules such as “don’t trust anyone”, “don’t express your feelings”, “don’t talk” are efforts by family members other than the alcohol addict to protect themselves. However, they negatively affect the development of individuals.
- Sometimes a “problem child” is chosen regarding family roles. In this way, attention is directed from the alcohol addict to the problematic child. Or the family member who takes on responsibilities and tasks that the alcohol addict does not perform is made into a hero. Some children are “silent” children who adapt passively to this environment. Unless a sensitive teacher notices, they rarely attract attention until adolescence. These children often develop alcohol problems.

According to American addiction centers’ publications in addition to the financial and emotional toll alcohol misuse can have, domestic violence and child abuse may occur. Research indicates that 92% of victims of domestic violence reported that the assailant had used alcohol or other drugs on the day of the assault. Another study found that of those individuals who attack a partner, 60 to 70% had misused alcohol. The prevalence of alcohol in abuse situations does not necessarily mean that drinking causes the domestic violence, but it may be a factor in the violence.

Some studies challenge the belief that there is a cause-and-effect relationship between alcohol misuse and domestic violence. For instance, the majority of men who are classified as “high-level drinkers” do not

abuse their partners. Rather, some researchers in the field of domestic violence postulate that the violent partner’s assaults are part of a pattern of abuse that is independent of alcohol consumption. Some individuals may use alcohol consumption to excuse their actions, but the blame is usually misplaced.

According to studies, children of alcoholic parents are more likely to have a series of mental and behavioral health problems such as Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), depression, anxiety disorders, attention problems, aggression, delinquency and behavioral disorders (Girling et al. 2006). In a study conducted by researchers on children aged 6-16 whose fathers were diagnosed with alcohol dependency and did not have any mental or physical disorders, they determined that children of fathers who were alcohol dependent had Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder, anxiety disorders, elimination disorders and depressive disorders more than children in the control group (Kultur et al. 2016). As alcoholic parents become more focused on drinking, they may become less loving, caring, nurturing and consistent within the family. They may not be able to provide adequate care for their children and may not be able to fulfill their parenting responsibilities. They may apply overly authoritarian or liberal styles within the family. They may be inconsistent in showing warmth and affection to their children and may have unrealistic expectations about their abilities (Erdim, 2009).

According to literature materials some of the impacts of alcohol users on their children were summarized:

- Low self-esteem;
- Experiencing emotional difficulties, feeling unloved;
- Behavioral problems at school (sudden changes in behavior, signs of neglect or physical/sexual abuse, compulsive behavior, shyness or avoidance of other children, argumentative or uncooperative behavior with teachers and classmates, reporting persistent health problems, etc.) and underachievement (such as difficulty concentrating, persistent absences, poor grades and/or failure to do homework, low grades on standardized tests).
- Experiencing social isolation. Feeling that bringing friends home is too problematic or embarrassing, or not being able to go out with friends because of responsibilities related to caring for other family members (e.g., siblings or dependent parents);
- Premature maturation;
- Having more difficulty transitioning from childhood to adolescence and being more likely to seek child protection and seek social services (Lima R. et al. 2015; Erdim, 2019)

Majority of people think that people who cannot control their alcohol use are mentally weak or even unbalanced. Many alcoholics see themselves this way. However, the real intention of alcoholism being seen as an illness is that the person loses their will and power to make choices in the face of alcohol. Accepting their powerlessness in the face of alcohol and seeking help is the first step and absolute requirement for a change

for the better. Millions of people have overcome the damage that alcohol has done to their social lives on this path that begins with this first step. People who accept that they are sick and are willing to get better benefit the most from treatment and self-help groups such as Alcoholics Anonymous. However, it is not necessary for the person to accept that they are an 'alcoholic' in order to receive treatment. What is important is that they consult a specialist, even for counseling purposes. Because the therapist's job is to convince the person that they need treatment, if they do. There are certain techniques for this. In the meantime, it should be noted that the effectiveness of addiction treatments and self-help groups has been definitively proven.

Conclusion: The main focus of health professionals working with families with addiction problems is to support families and prevent harm to children. A positive home environment is effective in reducing the effects of stress caused by parental alcohol addiction. In order to achieve this, health professionals working with children and families can take initiatives that ensure effective communication between family members, maintain stability, and reduce anxiety and depression (Ozturk, 2008, Girling, 2006, Erdim, 2019).

Children's needs can vary greatly. These may include identifying a support person at home to provide continuity of care, home visits to establish routines and boundaries, cognitive behavioral studies, personal and/or family therapy, opportunities to participate in social activities, creating time and space to talk to trusted adults, and opportunities to join a children's group. Child services in nurseries and preschools, school and community programs (e.g., breakfast clubs and structured after-school programs) may be effective interventions for this purpose (Velleman, 2007). Attending school, participating in clubs, and participating in sports can help young people develop self-esteem (Velleman, 2007). Adolescents' attachment to school has been identified as a protective factor.

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